

D5.1: Implementation Guide

[WP5 – Training programme implementation and sustainability of good practice]

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Abstract

This report documents on the implementation of irecs training modules in a real-world setting. Based on testing by pilot universities, experiences in using the irecs materials and evaluation of it, an implementation guide is designed for higher education institutions and RFO's. This will be disseminated through networks of EUA, ENERI, EUREC, EARMA, the Embassy of Good Science, ENRIO and ALLEA to facilitate embedding of results at institutional levels.

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Executive summary

irecs (<https://www.irecs.eu/>) is a Horizon Europe project that focuses on extended professionalisation of research ethics expertise, for research ethics bodies, students, PhD's and other professionals. irecs takes four science and technology cases as exemplars to tackle ethical challenges of new and emerging science and technology. The project aims to reinforce the reliability of science by advancing research ethics expertise and competencies. Effective dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) are key to maximising the project's impact: to improve the understanding of research ethics in Europe and to provide interactive, sustainable training programmes.

This report focuses on the implementation of irecs training modules in a real-world setting. Based on testing by pilot universities, experiences in using the irecs materials and evaluation of it, an implementation guide is designed for higher education institutions and RFO's.

This deliverable results from activities in task 5.3 specifically which concerns the piloting and testing of materials by pilot universities.

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
DEC	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
WP	Work package
REC	Research Ethics Committee
ECR	Early Career Researcher
SAB	Stakeholder Advisory Board

Table 1: List of acronyms/ abbreviations

1. Introduction

1.1 Objectives

irecs (<https://www.irecs.eu/>) is a Horizon Europe project that focuses on extended professionalisation of research ethics expertise, for research ethics bodies, students, PhD's and other professionals. irecs takes four science and technology cases as exemplars to tackle ethical challenges of new and emerging science and technology. The project aims to reinforce the reliability of science by advancing research ethics expertise and competencies. Effective dissemination, exploitation and communication (DEC) are key to maximising the project's impact: to improve the understanding of research ethics in Europe and to provide interactive, sustainable training programmes.

This report focuses on the implementation of irecs training modules in a real-world setting. Based on testing by pilot universities, experiences in using the irecs materials and evaluation of it, an implementation guide is designed for higher education institutions and RFO's.

This deliverable results from activities in task 5.3 specifically which concerns the piloting and testing of materials by pilot universities:

Task 5.3: Task Lead: UBO Contributors: EUA, EUREC, EARMA, UM, MEFST

Involve three pilot universities (UBO, UM, MEFST) to test all outputs, including the training programme and the proposed adaptations of ethics review processes, in a real-world setting. These universities will implement all outputs, and experiences will be evaluated (T1.5) to develop an implementation guide for higher education institutions, RPOs and RFOs. This will be disseminated through the networks of EUA, ENERI, EUREC, EARMA, the Embassy, ENRIO and ALLEA to facilitate embedding of results at institutional level.

2. Pilot universities: activities, opportunities and barriers

In this section, we report on progress and performance per dedicated dissemination and communication channel. While dissemination and communication have their distinct aims and target audiences, some overlap in the channels used was unavoidable.

The following three pilot universities are implementing concrete training programs at their facilities:

- University of Bonn (UBO)
- Maastricht University (UM)
- University of Split School of Medicine (MEFST)

2.1 UBO: University of Bonn

Bonn University employs 699 professors and 5 399 scientific staff, teaching more than 38 000 students, including more than 6 500 doctoral students. UBO's third-party fundraising efforts resulted in e.g. 69 ERC-grants hosted at UBO, and providing research ethics consultancy plays a strong role in this acquisition strategy. Ethics votes are currently provided by three different RECs: one at the Psychological Institute, another at the Center for Development Research (ZEF) and thirdly the Committee at the Medical Faculty. This latter REC was established to fulfil the requirements defined by German medical and pharmaceutical law. For years, it also provided ethics votes for projects unrelated to the medical or pharmaceutical field. Although this was a practical solution, it meant that the ethics reviews on these non-medical projects were conducted by REC members who, although being highly qualified in the fields that the medical REC was designed to cover, possibly have less expertise in non-medical research work and methods. Hence, in some cases external experts from the fields in question had to be recruited on a case-by-case basis.

To offer a better and more specialized research ethics support, the relevant infrastructure currently undergoes a process of fundamental improvement and restructuring. Based on the implementation guide described in more detail below, research ethics are to become an integral part of the research culture in Bonn.

In this process, UBO is benefitting from the irecs-materials in a multitude of ways:

- UBO developed the concept of a Research Ethics Curriculum to incorporate ethics teaching as a fixture into the education of UBO's scientists at all levels. Approximately, 100-200 undergraduate and postgraduate students from the life sciences and agriculture were trained in two semester-long courses using the irecs materials. Another training program is currently underway with around 100 participants.
- In cases where workshops or other training events are not immediate part of this Curriculum, parts of the irecs-materials are integrated into the material used. This allows for a flexible pick and match approach, ensuring that the course material actually meets the participants' needs, even if the course consists of small, very specialized groups.
- To ensure greater recognizability of irecs' outputs, a certificate was developed that can be obtained upon successful course completion.
- Furthermore, in order to ameliorate the abovementioned lack of specialized ethics review support, UBO is currently establishing a cross-faculty ethics committee additional to already existing RECs in Medicine, Psychology, Development Research and Dual Use issues. Despite the process being complex, first milestones have been achieved, such as developing rules of procedure and naming potential members. The irecs-material will in the future be used to train said members.

2.2 UM: Maastricht University

Research ethics is at the centre of the research agenda at Maastricht University (UM). The University has placed a comprehensive system of RECs to support its diverse research culture. UM has approximately 23,000 students and employs nearly 2,500 academic staff, including 411 doctoral researchers. It consists of six faculties that host 71 research institutes. A mandatory course on research ethics and integrity is provided to all PhD researchers during UM-wide training as well as at some graduate schools and research institutes within each faculty.

The ethical review of scientific research involving human participants or personal data is conducted by four ethical review committees. The accredited Medical Ethics Committee (Medisch Ethische Toetsingscommissie, METC) at the academic hospital - the Maastricht University Medical Centre+ (MUMC+), reviews and approves medical studies that fall under the Dutch law - Medical Research Involving Human Subjects Act (WMO), while the REC at the Faculty of Health, Medicine and Life Sciences (FHML-REC) reviews studies that are outside of the scope of the WMO. FHML-REC also issues “ethics licences” to specific Masters courses that enable them to appoint their own ethics assessors for low-risk thesis projects, with high-risk applications being sent to FHML-REC for review. Other types of scientific studies are reviewed by the Ethics Review Committee Inner City faculties and the Ethics Review Committee Psychology and Neuroscience. These two RECs often review studies in social and behavioural sciences that involve human subjects. Additionally, the UM-REC has been established to address overarching issues in research ethics across the three faculty RECs that review non-WMO studies.

irecs training materials are being integrated into MU's academic ecosystem as follows:

- Training courses on research ethics tailored to different audiences, taking into account the irecs training materials:
 - A webinar is scheduled for May 2025 for PhD candidates (up to 400) and other junior researchers (e.g., master's students) within the Care and Public Health Research Institute at the Faculty of Health, Medicine, and Life Sciences
 - We are planning webinars for REC members and supervisors of PhD and Masters students at the Faculty of Health, Medicine, and Life Sciences.
- Integration of irecs training materials in undergraduate and postgraduate education:
 - We are working to incorporate irecs online training materials in several courses within various Masters programmes in health and life sciences. Additionally, we are exploring the possibility of issuing certificates to students who complete the online modules as a part of their course assessment.
 - We are considering offering training courses on research ethics and integrity to undergraduate students within two bachelor's programmes in health sciences and social sciences.

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- Dissemination of irecs materials at Maastricht University
 - Information about irecs online training materials has been widely disseminated within the University. This includes meetings and email list outreach to REC members and over 200 junior and senior researchers across disciplines such as law, sustainability, business, and data sciences.
- Cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary forum on research ethics
 - We are working on an initiative to establish Research Ethics Forum to facilitate interdisciplinary exchange and discussion of research ethics issues within the University.
- Research in the field of research ethics
 - We are planning two studies on research ethics. One study will critically examine the use of AI tools in research, while the other will investigate the relationship between legal and ethical issues concerning privacy and security in developing AI models. These topics align with the implementation guide initiatives created by all the pilot universities to promote best practices for research ethics through research activities.

Lessons learned at UM:

- The benefits of issuing iRECs-certificates (e.g., certificates of completion) at the end of each module. As we work to incorporate iRECs' online training materials in several courses across multiple Master's programmes in health and life sciences, these certificates would greatly motivate both teachers and students to use the materials, as they can be used in course assessment.
- Establish an online forum where UM researchers can discuss and exchange ideas on questions and issues related to research ethics.
- Tailor the iRECs materials and provide research ethics training according to the needs of different audiences. For instance, feedback indicates that REC members and early career researchers have varying interests in different sections of the training materials. Their needs also differ based on the disciplines in which the researchers are working.

2.3 MEFST: University of Split School of Medicine

University of Split School of Medicine is a part of the University of Split, functioning as a separate legal entity but collaborating with other University constituents. This enabled us to reach out to the whole university to conduct a webinar with members of the RECs and researchers from other university constituents. Our main aim was to use the irecs training materials on AI in Health to train students in the topic that they are interested in and which will be a part of their future professional work.

After successfully piloting irecs training with students of medical studies (MD degree study), dental medicine studies (DMD degree study) and pharmacy studies (Master of Pharmacy study) (all programmes taught at the School of Medicine), we will incorporate irecs modules

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into the mandatory course on research methodology, taught at all study programmes. This will take effect from the 2025/2026 academic year.

We have also disseminated irecs materials to RECs at the University of Split (all University constituents have their separate RECs and the University has their own REC for research performed at the university level). We have done it through the e-mail dissemination of irecs materials and in meetings with REC representatives at some of the university constituents. The information about irecs training was also disseminated during the webinar with REC members and researcher from different university constituents.

We are also currently talking to the Croatian Science Foundation to organize a webinar on the ethics issues of AI in health for the applicants and beneficiaries of the major research funder in Croatia. We are also planning a national webinar in July 2025 for researchers in Croatia, in collaboration with the Department for Thematic Areas and Missions of Horizon Europe of the Croatian Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes.

We also working on academic and research ethics aspects of the use of AI in education. Mariano Kaliterna, MD, and Marija, the collaborator on the irecs project at MEFST has been inspired by irecs project to perform a study on using AI for writing student essays:

Kaliterna M, Žuljević MF, Ursić L, Krka J, Duplančić D. Testing the capacity of Bard and ChatGPT for writing essays on ethical dilemmas: A cross-sectional study. *Sci Rep.* 2024 Oct 30;14(1):26046. doi: 10.1038/s41598-024-77576-3.

Currently, we are working on the study on how the use of ChatGPT affects students' attitudes toward AI.

MEFST has so far organized 8 training events that involved 222 participants, predominantly for graduate students but also for REC members and researchers. Details are provided in Table 2.

Date	Format	Number of participants	Target Group	Modules
22 April 2025	Onsite	31	Graduate pharmacy students	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
1 April 2025	Onsite	64	Graduate medical students	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
21 March 2025	Onsite	17	Graduate medical students	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
20 March 2025	Onsite	26	Graduate medical students	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
19 March 2025	Onsite	24	Graduate medical students	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
6 March 2025	Onsite	30	Graduate dental medicine students	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
26 February 2025	Online	16	University REC members and researchers	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues

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23 January 2025	Onsite	14	Doctoral students, medicine	AI In Healthcare: Ethics Issues
Total		222		

Table 2 Training activities at MESFT

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In irecs, we see that a comprehensive research ethics infrastructure provides an important asset to the university's researchers of all levels, since – besides researchers' and the institution's own aspirations – various external factors require compliance with research ethics to an increasing extent. The demands come from:

- Funding agencies (in the form of ethics votes as well as ethics (self-)assessments and action plans, to be in place in order to receive funding)
- Scientific journals (in the form of ethics votes to be submitted along with the papers)
- National legal requirements regulating research (that are compulsory to follow)
- Society (to ensure their trust and thereby the foundation of all research)

In close cooperation, the pilot universities developed an Implementation Guide to help other research institutions in developing a structure meeting these requirements as well as their own needs, learning from the insights the pilot universities collected on their own journey.

This template contains various mechanisms for implementing a sound ethics policy at research institutions and universities, with special focus on research on and with new and emerging technologies. It is first and foremost aimed at policy makers at universities and RPO's but besides this primary target group shall also be helpful for other actors of the field. Not all of the template's pillars will be equally relevant for all universities and research institutions. Rather, the template can provide a roster along which to evaluate prevalent needs and identify points of action.

3.1 Four pillars of the Universities' RE Governance: Ethics by Training, Ethics by Design, Ethics by Scientific Discourse, Ethics by Exchange

Meeting the demands of funding agencies, journals, lawmakers and society can be achieved best and most sustainably by establishing a comprehensive research ethics infrastructure that includes four different areas. We see them as pillars carrying and supporting a university's or RPO's ethics culture. Policy makers committed to build such a culture should nurture each pillar to a certain degree matching the situation and needs at their institutions (each pillar will be further explained below):

1. Training offers (Ethics by Training)
2. Ethical Guidance and Support of Research (Ethics by Design)
3. Research in the field of Research Ethics (Ethics by Scientific Discourse)
4. Platforms to Communicate between all Actors (Ethics by Exchange)

All four pillars play into each other and need to communicate with each other as well as the university's faculties to ensure that the actual prevailing needs are addressed and met. This includes also taking into consideration what already exists at which level, which offers work or do not, and who are the actors who can contribute. Each of the pillars may aim at different target groups.

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1. Ethics by Training:

Providing scientists at all levels with the necessary knowledge on research ethics is the indispensable first step in establishing the culture that policy makers aim for. Without researchers having a thorough understanding of why research ethics are rightfully relevant for their work and how they are to implement it into their research work, all efforts to build a research ethics structure will remain fruitless. It is in the policy makers' responsibility to provide the necessary structures to at least facilitate, if not actively support these modes of qualification.

As always, it is crucial to meet the target groups' actual needs with the trainings' content and structure:

- For students
- For early career researchers
- For advanced career researchers
- For REC-members
- For lecturers & supervisors, as well as administrative staff working in the field

The concept behind these trainings is to introduce scientists to research ethics already at an early stage and throughout all career stages, thus establishing it a permanent fixture in research practice. Especially when working with new, emerging technologies, it is crucial that especially the early-career researchers gain an understanding of the ethical challenges that these technologies bring with them.

For example, at UBO, we developed an irecs-Certificate that the attendees can acquire, in order to create an additional incentive (see section below on UBO). UM intends to follow this example and issue certificates to participants.

Guiding questions to help organizations identifying their specific needs and limitations can be:

- *Who will be targeted? (Students? Researchers? REC-Members? Other groups)?*
- *What group size can be expected, and is doable?*
- *What is their level of prior knowledge on the topic?*
- *Is a specific focus needed or a generic (intro) to research ethics?*
- *How much person power and other resources are available?*
- *Practical considerations, such as whether the training should be on-site or remote?*
- ...

2. Ethics by Design:

Including ethical considerations from the very beginning of research design phase plays an important role in the (ethically) successful implementation of a project. The concept of

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Ethics by Design has become a central component when it comes to the development and implementation of new and emerging technologies. The European Commission refers to this as “[t]he aim of Ethics by Design is to incorporate ethical principles into the development process allowing that ethical issues are addressed as early as possible and followed up closely during research activities.”¹ Policy makers are to ensure for scientists to be able to practice this approach. Necessary in this context is not only providing the relevant training but also administrative research ethics support for researchers throughout the process at the institution. This includes:

- a. The integration of relevant research ethics topics in grant proposal writing and project development, supported by the advisory services offered to the individual scientists.
- b. The easy access to the relevant committees supporting the researchers, including RECs (as relevant for each project: cross-faculty, legally required (such as medical), or department- and professional-specific) but also committees and contact points on dual use, data protection, animal protection, etc., as applicable for the project.

Crucial in this regard is the well established as well as clearly communicated division of responsibilities between the committees at the research facility, as well as a transparent and pragmatic review process.

Good research ethics support is an asset and an integral part of a good research infrastructure. It must not be set up in a way that it hinders research and is thus considered an additional bureaucratic hoop the researchers are required to jump. Only if ethics support is provided in a pragmatic and genuinely helpful form, and if this widely known at the institutions as well as with the researchers, researchers will accept this offer.

Guiding questions to help organizations identifying their specific needs and limitations can be:

- *How aware are the researchers of ethics issues in general and in relation to the project they are planning? How much basic training is needed?*
- *How many applicants need support?*
- *Who can provide the consulting services?*
- *Which resources are available to be invested?*
- *What level of service can be guaranteed over longer periods?*
- ...

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/ethics-by-design-and-ethics-of-use-approaches-for-artificial-intelligence_he_en.pdf

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3. Ethics by Scientific Discourse:

To continuously improve research ethics procedures and requirements, research on Research Ethics as such is needed. Developing concepts of research ethics advances the field and provides the activities described above with a strong scientific foundation. Furthermore, it also fosters a culture of ethics with its own right in the institution.

4. Ethics by Exchange:

Regardless of which part of the areas of a research ethics structure an organization decides to establish or even just improve, the process ahead is a complex one with many layers, needs, actors to be included and branching. Establishing communicative pathways for all players to avoid duplicating mistakes, adopt proven best practices from each other and generate overall added value and learning opportunities is a resource that cannot be valued enough.

This includes building networks of like-minded colleagues, talking to the members of the target groups and incorporate the examples given and information gained into the individual strategy for the specific organization in question. Both policy makers and research support staff need these networks and this exchange to be able to work efficiently. Therefore, building a strong network benefits everybody and is well worth the effort.

3.2 How the pilot universities (can) use the implementation guide

The role of the pilot universities in irecs was designed to lead by example and point out paths of how to implement a culture of research ethics in an organization and beyond. This incorporated different aspects:

- To test the concepts as far as possible.
- To act as role models for other universities with similar structure
- To push communication and cooperation with regards to research ethics within their own organization and beyond
- To strengthen and facilitate communication between (pilot) universities, different RECs and networks

Furthermore, the Template can also be incorporated as part of the trainings to introduce the underlying structures to young researchers.

3.2.1 UBO

Currently, Bonn is especially working on two pillars: Research ethics training and the establishment of a central, cross-faculty Research Ethics Committee. Given the rather large size of UBO, both endeavours require following complex process.

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1. *The Training:*

With regards to training, we expanded the ethics courses since the beginning of the irecs-project, integrating the irecs-materials into UBO's academic ecosystem. More precisely, this includes:

- We provide regular training courses on various aspects of research ethics and research integrity, held at least once a semester for students and doctoral candidates in the life sciences, natural sciences and neurosciences, using the irecs training materials
- Furthermore, we are in the last steps of integrating the irecs-materials into a certificate that can be obtained upon successful participation in the various self-learning modules. For this, we cooperate with the Bonn Graduate Center (BGZ), the university's in-house provider for cross-faculty graduate trainings. On the technical side, we are using the platform "e-campus" (https://ecampus.uni-bonn.de/ilias.php?baseClass=ilrepositorygui&reloadpublic=1&cmd=frameset&ref_id=1&lang=en). Employing this common platform allows for easy scaling and transfer to other systems as well. Participants will receive the certificate after passing the respective module's set of exam questions. Once certification has been successfully established in Bonn, the aim is to implement it at the other pilot universities.

2. *A new cross-faculty Ethics Committee:*

In order to provide UBO's researchers with easily accessible, quick and research field specific ethics reviews, we are implementing a cross-faculty ethics committee. This REC will integrate the relevant university actors in one body working together, offering ethics reviews of projects of Bonn researchers. It is important to point out that – unlike the legally required ethics reviews for medical studies – due to the high value of freedom of research, these reviews are an offer that researchers can take advantage of on a voluntary basis.

- Given also the strong bottom-up structure of German universities, implementing a new acting body is a complex procedure. While this requires longer time until the committee can actually come into force, it also ensures that the committee has the support of the university as a whole. At UBO, the concept of a university-wide REC is strongly welcomed by the different parties, its necessity and added-benefit to the research life at UBO unquestioned.
- With the detailed concept as well as the Rules of Procedure ready in place, the REC currently awaits approval by the University's senate.

Furthermore, pillars 3 and 4 are strong in Bonn as well:

3. *Scientific discourse:*

With several groups and institutions working on ethics research – DRZE, IWE, Center for Life Ethics, as well as research groups in the faculties of theology and law, to name a selection – this research field is deeply rooted in UBO's culture, providing a constant influx of new ideas and concepts.

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4. *Exchange and Networking:*

Being in the process of implementing the cross-faculty ethics Committee, many new paths of exchange are currently forming. Furthermore, throughout the irecs-project a continuous exchange between researchers at DRZE and research administration staff was established, and we worked together closely to develop UBO's contribution to implementation guide presented here, reflecting insights from both scientific and practical implementation perspective.

3.2.2 UM

As indicated in section 2.2., training and research activities at UM have covered all four pillars identified in the template:

1. *Ethics training:*

Training based on irecs materials will be provided to PhD researchers and junior REC members. Ireccs materials will also be integrated into some undergraduate and postgraduate courses.

2. *Ethics by design:*

Training information and ireccs materials have been widely disseminated among various research institutes and REC members across all faculties. A list of grant officers and data managers at FHML has been compiled to identify potential stakeholders for future research ethics training or dissemination activities.

3. *Scientific discourse:*

Studies on research ethics are being developed. UM has experienced researchers working at several research institutes focusing on research ethics and integrity.

4. *Ethics by exchange:*

A UM initiative for cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary forum on research ethics.

3.2.3 MEFST

MEFST is working on all four pillars: Training (Ethics by Training), Ethical Guidance and Support of Research (Ethics by Design), Research in the field of Research Ethics (Ethics by Scientific Discourse) and Platforms to Communicate between all Actors (Ethics by Exchange).

1. *Training (Ethics by Training)*

We introduced training on research ethics and challenges to research ethics review into mandatory courses on research methodology (Department of Research in Biomedicine and Health) and medical humanities (Department of Medical Humanities). ireccs training materials are now included in courses for 1st to 3rd year of the curricula for medical, dental medicine and pharmacy students (Department of Research in Biomedicine and Health) and 4th to 6th year of the curricula for medical and dental medicine students (Department of Medical Humanities). The ireccs material we used focused on the ethics of AI in health, and we plan to include the topics on gene editing from the next academic year. This training will remain as a part of the mandatory courses for students.

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We have also introduced irecs training into the courses on ethics at the Doctoral School at MEFST, ensuring that doctoral students also learn about challenges to research ethics.

2. *Ethical Guidance and Support of Research (Ethics by Design)*

We closely collaborate with the Science office at MEFST and the Science Department of the University Hospital of Split, the main teaching hospital for the University of Split. In collaboration with them, we established the collaboration around ethics issues regarding emerging technologies and ethics challenges to health research.

We have also engaged with the Doctoral School at MEFST, where we have created the position of Research Integrity Advisor, which provided support for researcher about research ethics and research integrity.

3. *Research in the field of Research Ethics (Ethics by Scientific Discourse)*

We actively engage in research regarding emerging challenges to research ethics and integrity. Here are some articles published by our group, which were influenced by irecs topics:

Vasconcelos S, **Marušić A**. Gen AI and research integrity: Where to now? : The integration of Generative AI in the research process challenges well-established definitions of research integrity. *EMBO Rep.* 2025 Apr;26(8):1923-1928. doi: 10.1038/s44319-025-00424-6.

Roguljić M, Šimunović D, Buljan I, Žuljević MF, Turić A, **Marušić A**. Publishing Identifiable Patient Photographs in the Digital Age: Focus Group Study of Patients, Doctors, and Medical Students. *J Med Internet Res.* 2025 Mar 5;27:e59970. doi: 10.2196/59970.

Grošek Š, Štivić S, Borovečki A, Ćurković M, Lajović J, **Marušić A**, **Mijatović A**, Miksić M, Mimica S, Škrlep E, Lah Tomulić K, Erčulj V. Ethical attitudes and perspectives of AI use in medicine between Croatian and Slovenian faculty members of school of medicine: Cross-sectional study. *PLoS One.* 2024 Dec 5;19(12):e0310599. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0310599. PMID: 39637041; PMCID: PMC11620630.

Kaliterna M, Žuljević MF, Ursić L, Krka J, Duplančić D. Testing the capacity of Bard and ChatGPT for writing essays on ethical dilemmas: A cross-sectional study. *Sci Rep.* 2024 Oct 30;14(1):26046. doi: 10.1038/s41598-024-77576-3. PMID: 39472544; PMCID: PMC11522523.

We also have very good collaboration with the University's Office for Research – in collaboration with them we organized training for RECs at all University Schools and

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Departments, and offer them support in addressing the ethical issues related to emerging technologies.

4. *Platforms to Communicate between all Actors (Ethics by Exchange).*

We closely collaborate with the Croatian Network for Reproducibility and Integrity Network (CroRIN, <https://crorin.hr/en-homepage/>), where we have established contact with the Croatian Science Foundation, the main public research funding body in Croatia, and the Agency for Mobility and EU Programmes. We are currently planning irecs training events for July 2025.

4. Summary and outlook

This implementation guide represents a major milestone in the irecs project, showcasing how research ethics training and governance structures can be effectively embedded within diverse higher education and research environments. Drawing on insights from three pilot universities – UBO, UM, and MEFST – the guide demonstrates how tailored approaches, rooted in the irecs framework, support the development of robust, sustainable ethics infrastructures.

The four pillars – Ethics by Training, Ethics by Design, Ethics by Scientific Discourse, and Ethics by Exchange – have proven to be adaptable and scalable across institutions of varying size, culture, and regulatory context. Each university has implemented the pillars in ways that reflect their institutional strengths and needs, while jointly contributing to a shared vision for advancing research ethics across Europe.

Looking ahead, the implementation guide and associated training materials will continue to be disseminated via key networks including EUA, EUREC, EARMA, ENRIO, and ALLEA. The pilot universities will remain active as role models, offering tested strategies and fostering exchange with other institutions. The implementation guide will serve as a practical resource for universities and research-performing or funding organisations aiming to enhance their ethics ecosystems. A short, systematised version of the Implementation Guide is already available. It is to be distributed via our networks (see appendix).

Appendix

IMPLEMENTATION GUIDE

Institutional Best Practice for Research Ethics

A comprehensive research ethics infrastructure provides an important asset to the university's researchers of all levels, since – besides researchers' and the institution's own aspirations – various external factors require compliance with research ethics to an increasing extent. These external factors come across as requirements by funding agencies and scientific journals, the national legal requirements which regulate research, and public scrutiny.

The pilot universities (Bonn, Split, Maastricht) developed an Implementation Guide to help other higher education institutions and RFO's in developing a structure meeting these requirements as well as their own needs, learning from the insights the pilot universities collected on their own journey.

Strengthening responsibility and overall trust in science should be the leading objective of researchers and research institutions. This Implementation Guide is intended to help institutions to achieve this goal.

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The four pillars of the Universities' RE Governance

➤ Communication between all four pillars as well as the universities' faculties to ensure that actual needs are addressed and met:

- What is needed?
- What is already available?
- Where are gaps identified?
- What does or does not work in practice?
- Who provides what (and in which case)?

➤ Challenge here:

How to establish practical and sufficient pathways for communication without overdoing it (creating too much "communicative overhead" chipping away time and energy)?

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Ethics by Training

➤ Training according to the attendees needs

- For students
- For early career researchers
- For advanced career researchers
- For REC-members
- For lecturers & supervisors

Introducing researchers to ethics starting at an early stage and throughout all career stages, thus establishing it as a permanent fixture in research practice.

Ethics by Design

➤ (Administrative) Research ethics support:

- a. Implementation of relevant research ethics topics in grant proposal writing and project development, supported by individual advisory services offered
 - b. Easy access to the relevant/required committees supporting the researchers:
 - RECs: cross-faculty, legally required (medical), department- and professional-specific
 - But also: committees/contact points on dual use, data protection, animal protection.
- Crucial here is the well established and clearly communicated division of responsibilities between the existing committees, as well as a transparent and pragmatic review process.

Good research ethics support is an asset and an integral part of good research infrastructure. It must not be set up in a way that it hinders research and is thus considered an additional bureaucratic hoop the researchers are required to jump.

Only if ethics support is provided in a pragmatic and genuinely helpful form, and if this is widely known at the institutions, researchers will accept this offer.

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Ethics by Scientific Discourse

- Research on Research Ethics as such:
Developing RE-concepts to advance the field and support the activities with and on a strong scientific foundation.

This fosters a culture of ethics with its own right in the institution.

Ethics by Exchange

- Establishing communicative pathways for all players to avoid duplicating mistakes, adopt proven best practices from each other and generate overall added value and learning.
- Building networks of like-minded colleagues, talking to the members of the target groups and incorporate the examples given and information gained into the individual strategy for the specific organization in question.
- Both policy makers and research support staff need these networks and this exchange to be able to work efficiently.

Building a strong network benefits everybody and is well worth the effort.

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Role of the pilot universities
